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The Effectiveness of Interactive Lectures on Students' Knowledge and Attitude to Further Study

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ABSTRACT

One of the possible alternatives how to increase the chance of students' success in the STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) study programme is to supplement their lack of knowledge by using specific learning activities with the aim to motivate and activate freshmen. In our paper, we present the results that we gained from a standardized Force Concept Inventory (FCI) after implementing the intervention tool, interactive lectures. The overall results from the analysis of the FCI test point out that there was the increase in the students' knowledge. Even better results were achieved when students had the possibility to watch videos and use video analysis with the program Tracker (video analysis and simulations (VAS) method of problem tasks) in lectures as opposed to the groups taught by traditional methods. We have investigated how this intervention tool, interactive lectures, can support the students who are at-risk. We point out the importance of such intervention and its integration into study programme because thanks to these interactive lectures we can manage to reduce the lack of students' knowledge and increase their chances to cope with requirements of university study programme and eventually reduce the dropout rate.

Conference Key Areas: Physics and Engineering Education

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a regional education reform has been implemented in Slovakia with two main aims, firstly to enhance humanistic and creative teaching approaches and secondly to concentrate upon the development of the student's self-concept in order to achieve higher efficiency of learning. However, looking back at the outcomes of this reform, it seems that humanities and social science subjects were more or less knocking STEM and technical subjects down because the number of their lessons increased whereas mathematics and physics suffered from the reduction of lessons. Another outcome of this reform was that higher education was transformed to a three-level system, which triggered the need to adjust the study programs of individual departments as well as the content of the relevant subjects. And again the reduction affected mainly mathematics and physics and their number of lessons even so that the importance of these two subjects for technical study programmes is indisputable.

Another aim of the education reform was to increase the number of people with degree. In other words, to get as many students as possible to apply and enrol at universities, no matter whether they are prepared for it or not. As a result, vast majority of technical universities are attended by students who come from the whole spectrum of schools - secondary grammar schools or secondary technical schools - and a glaring gap in their readiness for university-level work is breathtaking. Furthermore, there was also a change in the system of the secondary school leaving examination. Students attending secondary technical schools can choose mathematics or physics only as an optional fifth subject! This is one of the reasons why students' theoretical knowledge, skills and key competencies are at very low level when they enrol at university. As a result, universities across our country are forced to spend time, money and energy to solve this disconnect. We must determine who is not prepared for university and attempt to get those students up to speed as quickly as possible or we risk losing them altogether.

Today more than before, education should meet the needs of practice and the content of it should be based on professional high-level expertise, which can be applied in a wide range of disciplines. Universities should have the leading role in preparing graduates who will follow new development trends in their field of study and whose knowledge will be supported not only by field-specific knowledge, but also by a broad range of skills and knowledge in mathematics and physics. Therefore, if we want to prepare graduates who are able to work independently with a high degree of creativity, then apart from well-educated teachers, devoted scientists, study materials of high quality and scientific laboratory equipment, we should keep in mind that university teachers of mathematics and physics must take into account the specific needs and requirements of each faculty and prepare specific study materials supporting the specialization of these faculties.

Therefore, we place the emphasis on the synthesis of theoretical knowledge and practical experience in the given field when teaching mathematics and physics in new accredited study programs of both the first and second level of higher education. So the graduate is able to conduct research and use evidence-based analysis, to gain in-depth knowledge in the major and analytic, problem solving, and to apply the knowledge of mathematics and physics in real-world settings either in production technologies, in the process of production management, or in quality control of the final products. Moreover, we try to prepare our students for teamwork and collaboration with

scientists and engineers, so they are able to work in interdisciplinary fields at the interface between physics and technical departments. As a result, we consider theoretical training not as the goal but as a means to an end, and therefore it should always be followed by practical application.

1 THE IMPACT OF INTERACTIVE LECTURES

As we have mentioned above, there is a glaring gap between students in their prior knowledge of mathematics and physics when they enrol at the Electrical Engineering Faculty. However, all of them have to attend and pass the examination from the subject entitled Introduction to Physics during their first semester if they want to continue in their studies and graduate successfully. To be more specific, they should acquire and understand the following topics: physics units, kinematics, dynamics, gravity, molecular physics, deformation, thermal physics, and thermodynamics that are covered during the lectures. However, most of our freshmen understand just the basics of these topics because their prior level of mathematics and physics knowledge is not always at the required level for STEM study programmes [1].

Therefore, we thought a lot about how to overcome this gap. We decided to support freshmen by interactive lectures using video and video analysis and find out whether interactive lecture are more effective in increasing students prior knowledge level of physics than traditional lectures.

At the beginning of the academic year 2016-2017, the Force Concept Inventory (FCI) was administered to students at Electrical Engineering Faculty to find out their prior knowledge level of physics. The FCI is a scientifically validated instrument that aims to measure students' conceptual understanding of Newtonian physics. The pre-test was carried out at the beginning of the semester during the first week and it was attended by 190 students. Post-test was carried out at the end of semester (the 13th week, after the semester course 'Introduction to Physics') and it was attended by 170 students.

The students were randomly assigned to two groups – the experimental (pre-test was attended by 98 students / post-test was attended by 75 students) and the control group (pre-test was attended by 92 students/ post-test was attended by 95 students). Only those students who participated actively in the lecture took part in the experimental group. The lectures for the experimental group were conducted in an interactive way aimed at clarity - using real-life videos related to the topic. All videos were analysed with the help of the program Tracker (using VAS method). In the control group, lectures were conducted in a traditional way. Students from both groups attended compulsory computational physics seminars. The subject 'Introduction to Physics' consists of 2 - 1 - 0 (lectures - exercises - labs) lessons per week, presence study. The semester consists of 13 weeks. Both experimental and control group had two lessons per week, that makes 26 lectures for each group per semester. The only difference between experimental and control group was that students from experimental group attended 26 interactive lectures while students from control group attended 26 classical lectures.

Fig. 1.Pre-test

Table 1. Pre-test - F-Test Two Sample for Variances and t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Equal Variances and Post-test - F-Test Two Sample for Variances and t-Test: Two Sample Assuming Unequal Variances

	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Experimental	Control	Experimental	Control
Mean	28.95	29.93	46.36	35.47
Variance	176.31	143.58	313.27	193.83
Observations	98	92	75	95
df	97	91	74	94
F	1.23		1.62	
P(F<=f) one-tail	0.16		0.014	
F Critical one-tail	1.41		1.43	
Pooled Variance	160.47		-	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		0	
df	188		138	
t Stat	-0.53		4.36	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.30		1.24E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.65		1.66	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.59		2.48E-05	
t Critical two-tail	1.97		1.98	

These results (Fig. 1, Tab. 1) indicate that there is no statistical difference in the mean pre-test FCI score of the experimental and the control group at the beginning of semester. But results in Fig. 2 and Tab. 1 indicate that there is statistical difference in

the mean post-test FCI score of the experimental and the control group at the end of semester.

*Fig. 2.*Post-test

Then we evaluated pair Student's t-test for experimental and the control group. The final numbers of students in the experimental and the control groups were reduced to 58 and 84 – only answers of those students were used who took part in both pre- and post-tests plus answered all questions.

*Fig. 3.*Paired Student's t-test for the experimental group

Table 2. t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means – the experimental group and the control group

	Experimental group		Control group	
	Post-test	Pre-test	Post-test	Pre-test
Mean	46.61	29.31	35.63	30.45
Variance	360.04	162.87	194.91	132.47
Observations	58	58	84	84
Pearson Correlation	0.69		0.65	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0		0	
df	57		83	
t Stat	9.57		4.35	
P(T<=t) one-tail	9.30E-14		1.94E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.67		1.66	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.86E-13		3.87E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.00		1.99	

The evaluation of post-test and pre-test of the experimental group at the beginning and end of semester (Fig. 3, Tab. 2) confirmed statistically significant difference between mean at the beginning and end of semester. The evaluation of post-test and pre-test score of the control group at the beginning and end of semester (Fig. 4, Tab. 2) confirmed statistically significant difference between mean at the beginning and end of semester, too, but p-value is lower in the case of the experimental group.

Fig. 4. Paired Student's t-test of the control group

Gain (Eq. 1) of courses was calculated in this way

$$g = \frac{\text{postscore\%} - \text{prescore\%}}{100 - \text{prescore\%}} \quad (1)$$

was $g_{\text{exp}} = 0.22$ for experimental group and $g_{\text{cont}} = 0.08$ for control group.

2 DISCUSSION

As the authors claim [2] it is necessary to point out that 60% of FCI test, for empirical reasons, is minimal threshold so that a student could continue in understanding Newtonian mechanics effectively. Below this threshold, a student's grasp of Newtonian concepts is insufficient for effective problem solving. Otherwise a student is not able to overcome difficulties which caused him/her misconception and thus s/he learns physics by heart. 80 – 85% FCI score represents the mastery level when a student thinks in terms of intentions and Newtonian physics. As the authors state such an outcome does not depend on what teacher, in what country and what kind of school s/he teaches [3 - 6]. The results of pre-test (Fig. 1) reveal that only 4(5)% of students (in the experimental/control group) reached the level of 60% or higher from FCI score and in post-test 19(2)% (Fig. 2).

The low growth of successful students can be caused by the fact that only one third of the total number of students attended lectures. In the experimental group final number of students attended lectures decreases to 60% in comparison with the beginning of semester.

The final successfulness of course 'Introduction to Physics' in academic year 2016/17 was 86% (45% of exam results was with the grade E); 70% of freshmen fulfilled the requirements of the subject „Mathematics 1“. Students who actively attended lectures of „Physics 1“ this semester after attending “Introduction to Physics” reached the level of 60% of FCI score in average [7].

3 SUMMARY

Student t-test confirmed statistical significant difference in knowledge and conception of Newtonian mechanics at the end of the semester in comparison with the prior knowledge level for both the experimental and the control group. However, our results also confirmed that there is statistical difference in the mean of post-test FCI score of the experimental group in comparison with the control group at the end of semester.

Watching real physics concept videos and their subsequent video analysis had a positive impact on the growth of knowledge and improving of conception of Newtonian mechanics at the end of the semester as was declared in previous studies by other authors [8 - 12].

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